

Variable importance is variance, not effect size: a caution and a prevalence screen

Christian Theil Have

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Abstract

Mean-decrease-in-impurity (MDI) variable importance is the default, cheapest way to read a random forest, and it is routinely misread as a per-unit effect size, as if it were comparable to a linear-model coefficient. In additive settings MDI instead estimates each feature’s *variance contribution*, $\text{Var}(f_j(X_j))$ — for a linear term, $\beta_j^2 \text{Var}(X_j)$. We make the practical consequences concrete through five controlled experiments: impurity importance (i) grows with the *square* of a linear coefficient, not the coefficient; (ii) assigns an interaction’s variance to the interacting variables; and (iii) gives *provably identical* scores to a genuinely non-linear effect and to a linear effect on a skewed feature, because the two contribute identical variance. These are not artefacts of the well-known bias toward high-cardinality, continuous, or correlated features: they arise among features that are continuous, uncorrelated, and identically distributed, and they are not specific to impurity: permutation importance behaves the same way, and standardised regression coefficients spread similarly. No marginal importance measure separates an effect’s *shape* from a feature’s *distribution*; partial-dependence plots do. Finally, an LLM-assisted screen of the ranger-citing literature, an unvalidated estimate rather than an audit, suggests that about one in six papers that interpret an impurity ranking rely on it without such corroboration, including heavily-cited work.

1 Background

For a random forest [1], the impurity importance of a feature is the total decrease in node impurity attributable to splits on that feature, summed over all splits and all trees. For classification the impurity is Gini; for regression there is no class label at a node, so **ranger** [10] (and most implementations) use **response variance** as the impurity proxy — a split is scored by how much it reduces the sum of within-child variances. This substitution is the source of every effect studied here.

Two strands of prior work bear on this. The first documents that MDI is *biased* toward continuous and high-cardinality features and inflates correlated predictors [3, 12]; Nembrini et al. give the bias-corrected “actual impurity reduction” (AIR), exposed by **ranger** as `impurity_corrected`. The second is theoretical: Louppe et al. [6] decompose asymptotic MDI into per-variable contributions, and Scornet [15] proves that for additive regression with independent inputs MDI recovers a *variance-explained* decomposition, each feature’s score tracking $\text{Var}(f_j(X_j))$, which for a linear term is $\beta_j^2 \text{Var}(X_j)$.

Our experiments are consequences of that identity, not new biases. Their value is to show, among features that are continuous, uncorrelated, and identically distributed (where the type-bias literature does not apply), how far a variance-contribution measure departs from a per-unit effect size, and that it *provably cannot* separate an effect’s shape from a feature’s distribution.

The new contribution is thus the sharp skew-versus-nonlinearity demonstration and an estimate (Sections 8.1–8.2) of how often the misreading reaches published conclusions.

All experiments use `ranger` 0.18.0; the code that generates them and the figures is available with the rest of the supporting material (Section 10). Unless noted, importances are the plain `impurity` measure (the one the definition above describes); Section 2 compares it against `impurity_corrected`.

2 Linear effects: importance is in squared-coefficient units

Data: $y = a + 2b + 4c$, with $a, b, c \sim U(0, 1)$, $n = 1000$. OOB $R^2 = 0.98$. Impurity importance (abbreviated “vip”, variable importance) ranks the features in the correct order, but its *ratios* do not match the coefficient ratios:

feature	OLS coef	impurity vip (ratio)	impurity_corrected (ratio)
a	1	1.00	1.00
b	2	2.32	5.31
c	4	7.79	23.1

A coefficient ratio of 1 : 2 : 4 becomes an importance ratio of 1 : 2.3 : 7.8 — close to 1 : 4 : 16, the ratio of the *squared* coefficients. This is not a distortion but the variance-contribution identity of Section 1 made visible: for a linear term the contributed variance is $\beta_j^2 \text{Var}(X_j)$, and here $\text{Var}(X_j) = 1/12$ is common to all features, so importance should track β_j^2 . Extending to $y = a + 2b + 3c + \dots + 11k$ (11 features, coefficients 1 . . . 11) confirms it: regressing importance on β^2 — a single, non-nested predictor — gives $R^2 = 0.99$, versus $R^2 = 0.91$ on β (Fig. 1). Importance is denominated in squared-coefficient (variance) units, not coefficient units.

The bias correction does not help: `impurity_corrected` is also variance-based, and its ratios (1 : 5.3 : 23) are if anything more spread.

Takeaway. Importance answers “which feature matters more” reliably for linear effects, but “how much more” is not comparable to a coefficient.

3 Interactions are charged to the interacting variables

Data: a pure three-way parity interaction with no marginal or pairwise effects,

$$y = c/10 + ((a + b + d) \bmod 2), \quad a, b, d, c \in \{0, 1\}, \quad n = 10000.$$

No single variable, and no pair, among a, b, d carries information about y ; only the joint parity of all three does. c has a small independent effect. (Two-way parity would not do: for binary inputs $(a + b) \bmod 2 = a + b - 2ab$ is bilinear, so OLS with an $a \times b$ term fits it exactly. Three-way parity is the smallest a standard interaction term cannot recover.)

- **OLS** stays blind even with all pairwise products: a model in a, b, d and $a \times b, a \times d, b \times d$ still reaches only $R^2 = 0.01$, all coefficients ≈ 0 except c (≈ 0.10). Only the three-way product $a \times b \times d$ recovers the signal, which one rarely adds unprompted.
- **Random forest** captures it (OOB $R^2 = 0.73$), and impurity importance loads on the interacting variables: $\text{vip}(a)=346$, $\text{vip}(b)=422$, $\text{vip}(d)=432$, $\text{vip}(c)=30$ (Fig. 2), outranking c , the only variable with a marginal effect, by an order of magnitude.

Figure 1: Impurity importance against the coefficient β (left, curved) and against the variance contribution β^2 (right, linear, $R^2 = 0.99$). Importance is linear in β^2 , not in β .

Takeaway. A high importance need not imply any marginal effect: importance surfaces variables that matter only in combination, exactly the ones a linear model drops. Importance and coefficients measure different things.

4 What the split criterion sees, and what it discards

Two properties of variance-based splitting explain the rest of the paper. Take a noise-free, sorted dataset and sweep every single split, scoring each by the sum of within-child variances, for $y = x$, $y = x^2$, $y = x^3$ ($x = 1 \dots 1000$):

response	raw min split-variance	frac. of parent variance removed	argmin index (of 1000)
x	4.2×10^4	0.75	500 (centre)
x^2	4.3×10^{10}	0.76	697
x^3	4.1×10^{16}	0.74	799

The raw minimum grows by orders of magnitude with the degree, but that is a *response-scale artifact*: as a fraction of parent variance removed, all three splits are essentially equal (≈ 0.75). A “large scale wins” story does not survive normalisation; two things do.

1. **Trees discard feature-distribution shape.** A split compares only the *order* of a feature’s values, so the tree is invariant to any monotone transform and cannot see whether a feature is uniform or heavy-tailed, information a per-unit effect size needs. This is the root cause of the confound in Section 6.
2. **The optimal split migrates with response shape.** For a linear response the best split is central; for higher orders it moves toward the high- y tail ($500 \rightarrow 697 \rightarrow 799$). The imbalance

Figure 2: Same data, two views. OLS with all main and pairwise terms assigns a, b, d (and every pairwise product) essentially zero coefficient, seeing only c ; RF impurity importance ranks the three interacting variables highest.

leaves more structure in the large child, so more splits follow down that branch, each charged to the same feature.

So importance summarises *variance contribution over the feature ordering*, blind to the metric the ordering lives on.

5 Non-linear effects: variance contribution predicts the ranking

Data: $y = a + b^2 + c^3$, with $a, b, c = 1 + U$ and $U \sim U(0, 1)$, $n = 10000$. Each term’s variance contribution grows with its degree, so Section 1 predicts $\text{vip}(a) < \text{vip}(b) < \text{vip}(c)$; the forest confirms it, $1780 < 8168 < 39570$ (a 1 : 4.6 : 22 ratio). A linear model still returns non-zero coefficients, but they are uninterpretable: the residuals are visibly non-normal.

6 Non-linearity and feature scale are indistinguishable

The identity of Section 1 has a jarring consequence, which the following construction makes concrete. Take equal linear effects but skewed feature *distributions*:

$$a = 1 + U, \quad b = (1 + U)^2, \quad c = (1 + U)^3, \quad y = a + b + c, \quad n = 10000.$$

Every feature enters with coefficient 1, and OLS recovers 1.00, 1.00, 1.00: nothing about the *effects* is non-linear. Yet the forest reports **1780 / 8168 / 39570**, a 1 : 4.6 : 22 spread **numerically identical**, to the digit, to the non-linear model of Section 5 (Fig. 3). The identity is *provable*: with the same U draws, $b = (1 + U)^2$ under a linear effect is a monotone relabelling of the uniform feature under a b^2 effect, and y is identical. Since a tree sees only feature *order* (Section 4), the splits, and every importance, must match. Trees discard exactly the distribution-shape information that would tell the two apart.

This is **not specific to impurity**. Permutation importance gives the same ratios in both worlds (1 : 9.0 : 49.3 vs. 1 : 9.1 : 50.1), and standardised OLS coefficients spread (1 : 3.0 : 7.0): all

summarise variance contribution, identical across the two worlds. It is a property of any marginal importance; the only remedy is a shape-aware view such as a partial-dependence plot.

Figure 3: Provably identical importances from two different worlds. Left: genuinely non-linear effects. Right: linear effects on skewed features. No marginal importance measure can distinguish them.

Takeaway. A tall importance bar can mean a strong or non-linear effect, or merely a heavy-tailed feature; no marginal importance can say which.

7 Practical guidance

1. **Read importance ordinally, not as an effect size.** Treat it as a ranked shortlist among comparable features, never as a magnitude to line up against OLS coefficients. A high bar may reflect a marginal effect, an interaction (Section 3), a non-linear effect (Section 5), or merely a skewed feature distribution (Section 6).
2. **Disambiguate with partial-dependence plots.** PDPs [2] recover exactly what importance discards: in Section 6 the skewed-feature model’s PDPs are straight lines while the non-linear model’s curve — same importances, different shapes. For the Section 3 interaction, a one- or two-way PDP among a, b, d is flat — the parity pattern only appears in the full three-way view — which is itself the tell that the effect is a higher-order interaction that per-feature importance has flattened. Curvature (or a suspiciously flat low-order PDP over a high-importance variable) is a concrete cue to add a polynomial or interaction term back into an interpretable model.
3. **impurity_corrected fixes a different problem.** It removes the bias toward null / high-cardinality features (use it — it is the right default), but it does not make importances scale-comparable across real effects; if anything it widens the spread (Section 2). Debaised MDI variants exist [7, 14] but target the same type-bias, not the shape/scale reading examined here.
4. **Switching to permutation importance does not fix the shape/skew conflation.** Permutation and conditional [4] importances address other problems (and are worth using), but as Section 6 shows they too summarise variance contribution and cannot separate effect shape from feature distribution. Only a shape-aware view (PDP/ALE [2, 13], SHAP [9]) does that.

5. **If you know the structure is linear, use the linear model.** Random forests buy you interaction- and non-linearity-detection; when there is nothing to detect, OLS is both more accurate and directly interpretable.

8 Prevalence in the literature

The preceding sections establish, in controlled settings, how a variance-contribution measure can be misread as an effect size. To estimate how often that misreading reaches published conclusions, we screened the literature that uses the `ranger` R package — one of the most widely used random-forest implementations, and the one whose importances these results concern. We screen for papers whose stated conclusions depend on the magnitude or ranking of an impurity importance without the corroboration that would guard against the effects of Sections 2–6.

8.1 Method

Corpus. We took every work recorded by OpenAlex as citing the `ranger` reference publication [10] (OpenAlex work `W2157395790`), 3,189 works in total. For each we retrieved bibliographic metadata from OpenAlex and, where an open-access full text was available, the full text from Europe PMC; 773 works had retrievable open-access full text. Screening was restricted to these, because the detail needed to judge exposure — which importance measure is used, and whether it is corroborated — is almost never present in an abstract.

Relevance filter. Many papers cite `ranger` only for its speed or for prediction and never interpret a variable importance. To drop these without discarding relevant work, we required a textual mention of variable importance: a paper was retained if its full text matched, case-insensitively, any of the following regular-expression alternatives.

```
(variable|feature|permutation|gini|impurity)\s+importance
importance\s+(score|value|ranking|measure)
mean decrease
decrease in (impurity|gini|accuracy)
\bMDI\b \bMDA\b \bBoruta\b
impurity[_\s]?corrected
most important (variable|feature|predictor)
```

524 of the 773 matched. The filter is deliberately broad: an earlier version that also required a significance keyword (`importance_pvalues`, Altmann, Janitza, Boruta) missed most exposed papers. Of 40 sampled papers it rejected, 24 still used an impurity importance and 11 met the flag criterion below, because many papers rank features by impurity importance with no significance test. In total 544 papers were screened: the 524 matches plus 20 from earlier passes (including that probe) that the broadened filter misses. Its recall was not separately re-estimated (see limitations).

Two-stage screen. Each paper was read by a large language model under a fixed instruction and asked to return a structured judgement; the verbatim prompts are in the supporting repository (Section 10). The screen has two stages using different models, so that the second acts as an adversarial check on the first.

Stage 1 — screening. A first model (Claude Haiku 4.5) read each paper and recorded which importance measure it uses, whether it interprets that importance’s magnitude or ranking, which

corroborating analyses it reports, and a flag for whether a central conclusion could have been affected. The instruction was explicit that the bias corrupts magnitude and ranking, not the binary verdict that a variable is used, so a significant importance p -value (Altmann [5], Janitza [11], Boruta [8]) does not by itself protect a conclusion. A paper was flagged only if it leaned on the magnitude or ranking of an impurity importance for a central conclusion *without* corroboration, defined as permutation importance, SHAP [9], partial-dependence/ALE [2, 13], conditional importance [4], or held-out validation of the *selected* features (overall test accuracy does not count, as it validates prediction, not the ranking). Every flag required a quoted passage.

Stage 2 — adjudication. Every flagged paper was independently re-read by a second, stronger model (Claude Sonnet 5) under an explicitly adversarial instruction: its task was to *refute* the flag. It returned a verdict of *confirmed*, *refuted*, or *uncertain*, and confirmed only when all three conditions held at once: 1) the paper genuinely uses an impurity (not solely a permutation or SHAP) importance, 2) the ranking is central to a stated conclusion, and 3) the ranking is not adequately corroborated. Both models were accessed in July 2026. Using two models from a single vendor means the adjudication is a precision filter, not an independent validation — a different-vendor or human check would be stronger; we return to this in the limitations.

8.2 Results

Table 1 traces the corpus through the pipeline. Of the 544 papers screened, 306 were judged to use an impurity importance and 125 were flagged in stage 1. The adversarial adjudication confirmed 55, refuted 65, and could not decide for 5, overturning roughly 56% of the stage-1 flags. The implied stage-1 precision is therefore about 44%, and raw screening counts should be discounted accordingly.

Table 1: The ranger-citing corpus traced through the screening pipeline. The final rows are counts of screened papers; percentages in the text are relative to the 544 screened.

Stage	Count
Works citing ranger (OpenAlex)	3,189
With open-access full text	773
Matching the relevance filter	524
Screened (filter matches + non-match sample)	544
Using an impurity importance (stage 1)	306
Flagged (stage 1, Haiku 4.5)	125
Confirmed (stage 2, Sonnet 5)	55
Refuted	65
Uncertain	5

Note: the 544 screened papers comprise all 524 filter matches plus 20 non-matching papers that were screened in earlier passes before the filter was finalised, including the random recall sample; all 524 filter matches were screened.

Taking the confirmed count in Table 1 at face value, 55 of the 544 screened papers state a central conclusion that could have been distorted by the effects of Sections 2–6 and did not cross-check it. That is about 10% of the screened papers. Measured against the 306 that actually interpret an impurity importance, it is 18%, roughly one in six. As a share of all 773 full-text ranger-citing works it is about 7%.

Two features of the confirmed set are worth drawing out. First, exposure is concentrated in

papers that use no significance machinery: 51 of the 55 confirmed papers (93%) report no importance p -value or Boruta selection and simply rank features by impurity importance, suggesting that familiarity with significance testing goes with more cautious interpretation of a ranking. Second, the confirmed papers are not confined to low-visibility venues: citation counts span the full range of the corpus (median 11, versus a corpus median of 10), and 12 of the 55 exceed 50 citations.

Limitations. These are model judgements, not audits: a flag means a conclusion *could* have been affected and was uncorroborated, not that it is wrong, and predictive accuracy is unaffected. The 10% is an unvalidated estimate; stage 2 raises precision but is not independent validation, and there is no human ground truth. Only 773 of 3,189 works had open-access full text, and open access correlates with field and venue, so the sample may not generalise. The broadened filter’s recall was not re-estimated. The repository lists flagged papers by identifier; we treat this as a claim about corroboration practice, not correctness, with each flag backed by a quoted passage.

9 Conclusion

Impurity importance estimates a feature’s variance contribution, not its per-unit effect. Read that way its behaviour is unsurprising: it scales with the square of a linear coefficient, assigns an interaction’s variance to the interacting variables, and gives identical scores to a non-linear effect and to a linear effect on a skewed feature. That last identity is provable, and it holds for permutation importance too, so it is a property of variance-based measures rather than a defect of MDI. The mechanisms are largely established; our contribution is the sharp skew-versus-nonlinearity demonstration and an estimate of how far the misreading reaches. In the screened literature, 18% of the papers that interpret an impurity ranking, including heavily-cited work, lean on it without corroboration. Impurity importance is a useful screening tool when read as a ranked shortlist and paired with partial-dependence plots. It misleads when read as an effect size.

10 Data and code availability

All code and data supporting this paper are available at <https://github.com/cth/rf-impurity>: the R scripts that generate the controlled experiments and figures of Sections 2–6 (with a one-line command to reproduce every number cited there), the corpus-construction and full-text-retrieval pipeline, the relevance filter, the verbatim screening and adjudication prompts, and the per-paper structured records and verdicts behind Section 8.2.

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